

CONTENTS

GOSPEL: AN ACT OF COMMUNION WITH GOD	<i>Divya Sharma</i>	1
ISSUES CONFRONTING BORDER REGIONS IN JAMMU : EMERGING TRENDS	<i>Sapna K Sangra</i>	25
SANSKRIT ORIGIN WORDS IN THAI LANGUAGE	<i>Kedar Nath Sharma</i>	41
ACCEPTANCE OF ICT BASED INFORMATION RESOURCES AMONG LIBRARY USERS' OF NIT KURUKSHETRA AND MNIT JAIPUR	<i>Ajay Kumar Arora and Sanjeev Sharma</i>	56
SHYNESS AND LONELINESS: A COMPARISON BETWEEN LADAKHI AND JAMMU STUDENTS	<i>Chandra Shekhar, Aditya Jamwal & Promila Raina</i>	69
LADAKH AUTONOMOUS HILL DEVELOPMENT COUNCILS POLICIES AND STRATEGIES	<i>Gulam Murtaza</i>	79
HINDU WOMEN'S RIGHT TO PROPERTY: AN EVOLUTION FROM SHASTRIC LAWS TO THE PRESENT ERA	<i>Vandita Sharma</i>	92
PREVENTIVE LEGAL AID IN INDIA: AN OVERVIEW	<i>Musadir Farooq</i>	107
POSTMODERNISM IN PHILIP ROTH'S THE COUNTER-LIFE, OPERATION SHYLOCK: A CONFESSION AND THE PLOT AGAINST AMERICA	<i>Shivani Sharma</i>	120
WOMEN AND MUSLIM PERSONAL LAW IN INDIA	<i>Raveena Choudhary</i>	134
PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL OF SELF EMPLOYMENT SCHEME FOR EDUCATED UNEMPLOYED YOUTH IN JAMMU DIVISION	<i>Lalit Kumar Gaiind</i>	146
E-RESOURCES: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES IN INDIA	<i>Tarseem Singh</i>	153
वेदप्रतिपादित भाषा उत्पत्ति विशयक मूल अवधारणा – (ध्वनि के विशेष सन्दर्भ में)	<i>सत्यप्रिय आर्य</i>	166
भूमण्डलीकरण के दौर में हिन्दी भाषा	<i>बन्दना जम्वाल</i>	177
टिँडुपाला दी वषा मँदेरठा	<i>म. गरनिसर सिंथ</i>	182

Researcher

A Multi-disciplinary Journal

**UNIVERSITY OF JAMMU
JAMMU**

RESEARCHER

A Multi disciplinary Journal

Vol. IIX No. 1, 2016 ISSN 2278-9022

University of Jammu
JAMMU

GOSPEL: AN ACT OF COMMUNION WITH GOD

*Divya Sharma**

They came out of the South unknown to me, one by one, and yet at once I knew them as of me and mine.

Du Bois, W. E. B. "The Sorrow Songs." The Souls of Black Folk. 1903
God writes the Gospel not in the Bible alone, but also on trees, and in the flowers and clouds and stars.

Martin Luther King
When you sing gospel you have a feeling there is a cure for what's wrong.

Mahalia Jackson

ABSTRACT

The article explores the rich terrain of the genre of gospel from the pre-civil war period affirming that the gospel lyrics defamiliarized the familiar and common place into extraordinary and original through transformative imagination further translated through performances. Building on the ideas of black feminists/womanists who were a significant part of the black liberation movement/black arts movement inspired by the developments of the black power movement that brought forth the black aesthetic, the article discusses the intersecting grounds at which the womanism and ecofeminism seems to meet, eventually gravitating towards a detailed ecofeminist analysis of the genre, its developments, and thematic concerns, along with the key women artists' oeuvre.

Keywords : Gospel, Ecofeminism, Black feminism/womanism, Black aesthetic

Introduction

United States broke away from England during the revolutionary era. The thirteen American colonies adopted the Declaration of

*Ph.D. Scholar, Department of English, University of Jammu, Jammu.

Independence on July 4, 1776, declaring themselves a new nation (i.e. independent sovereign states), the United States of America, no longer identifying themselves as a part of the British empire. The Achilles heel of this development however remained that it did not cover the population that was black. While the Abolitionist movement was founded in 1789, black as well as white people who supported the cause of abolition of slavery kept growing. During the Cold war era the pre-civil war period ushered in the strong wave for the abolition of slavery. The period from 1954 to 1964 covering the Civil Rights movement, that gained ground in the shape of the Civil Rights Act of 1964, in the post war struggle for black liberation was also the period of the Gospel spirituals and was followed by the black power movement from 1964 to 1973 that saw the blossoming of the blues. During the Civil Rights movement there was a growing resistance against segregation that led to the formation of activist non violent organizations. A thrust on the philosophy of racial integrationism led to victories that were significant and registered in the courts as well as mass media. The black power movement's political agenda was to bring about a shift towards separatism and nationalism, endorsing active methods of resistance such as riots, seditions, and revolution over passive non-violent means. The black power movement brought the focus on the poor and lower class blacks as well as the white middle class activist constituencies, from the white Euro-American traditions as standard of values. The Black liberation movement or the Black movement marked the "New Renaissance" or the rebirth of the black (poetry, drama, fiction, and literary criticism). Significantly black criticism took on a new splendour in the works of writers Amiri Baraka and Larry Neal, the editor Hoyt Fuller, and the academic critics Addison Gayle, Jr., Stephen Henderson, and Darwin T. Turner bear witness to this statement. Following these developments in 1970s and the 1980s two significant

phenomena occurred. One, a younger generation of black critics emerged namely, Houston A. Baker, Jr., and Henry Louis Gates, Jr. and two, a distinctive black feminism came to the fore in the critical works of Toni Cade Bambara, Mari Evans, Audre Lorde, Alice Walker, and academic critics such as Barbara Smith, Erlene Stetson, and Mary Helen Washington. The period marked much energy being expended in scholarship and pedagogy centred around the institutionalisation of black studies programs, which first began to appear in the late 1960s and which preoccupied university intellectuals through the 1980s. It is interesting to note how the black aesthetic that culminated as a product of the Black Power movement intersects with the womanist and ecofeminist ideas. For the Blacks in America the journey of black aesthetic is that of cultural nationalism to political internationalism and phenomenological poetics to black aesthetics and black nationalism. Instrumental in this journey have been Malcolm X, with his philosophy of black power (freedom from oppression, devotion to black solidarity, integration for cultural autonomy, accountability and responsibility towards community), Hoyt W. Fuller with his belief that black community needs to recover and revere their distinctive cultural roots, "mystique of blackness" (that transpires as freedom from the influence of white racist cultural values), a celebration of distinctive styles, rhythms, techniques of black music and black language, and a need to facilitate the emergence of new black critics, Larry Neal who reviewed the efforts of new black artists in order to break away from the dominant white artistic and creative modes for the pioneering of new African tradition, and form a personalised culture. In accordance to his cultural theory as derived from Frantz Fanon and Ron Karenga, he gave a call for the jettisoning of the mainstream standards of ethnic artistic and modes developing anew, attempting to anchor the emerging black aesthetic in a ritualistic theory of art reminiscent of the

myth critic Francis Fergusson, he casted black music as the fundamental primordial form of black expression and wanted black poetry to eschew textualism and return to ritualistic oral performance (through the aid of the twin tools of communal music and oral folktale) to become an integral part of the black life. Stokely Carmichael who realized the need to abolish the dependent colonial status inflicted upon the black community and that the social and cultural personality of the black community must be preserved and the community must win its freedom while preserving its cultural integrity, and LeRoi Jones (Armi Baraka) who was associated with the avant-garde Beat Generation. Baraka in his early phenomenological theory of art insisted on the primacy of process over product, of function over form, of art-making over artefacts, of spirit over matter, of being (verb) over Being (noun), constituting an assault on formalist poetics. He proclaimed that politics, social theory, religion, and art all produced orderly patterns of images fostering cultural consciousness and national autonomy, rejecting his prior anti-mimetic and anti-formalist philosophy of art because he believed that black art must have social and political dimensions. The privatised expressionism of phenomenological poetics needed to be scrapped for a black artists goal must be to report and reflect accurately the nature of society so that other men will be moved by the exactness of the rendering, the socio-political mission of black art required a combined didactic-affective poetics rooted in mimesis. Baraka sums up the spirit of the Black Aesthetic in the poem "Black Art" in *Black Magic: Collected Poetry 1961-1967* which promoted revolutionary activity at the time. Baraka writes: "We want "poems that kill./Assassin poems, poems that shoot/ guns. Poems that wrestle cops into alleys/and take their weapons leaving them dead/with tongues pulled out.

Black feminist criticism emerged as an offshoot of the black aesthetics in the early 1970s, it made its debut in print during the

late 1970s. While realizing their oppressive restrictive social situation, black women while still being cognizant of their anger and isolation kept advocating for the wider black liberation movement in their fight against race and class oppression; hand in hand with black men. However the call for separatism within black feminism was in relation to white society and white feminism. The advent of 1970s and 1980s in the history of black feminism brought in public the ground-breaking literary storehouse of works by black feminists such as Toni Cade Bambara, Barbara Christian, Mari Evans, bell hooks, Gloria T. Hull, Andre Lorde, Barbara Smith, Erlene Stetson, Alice Walker, and Mary Helen Washington. The main focus of these feminists remained: the condition of other Third world women, race and class based oppression, usefulness of female solidarity, the particular social situation faced by black women, patriarchalism, the history of women's literature, and the scope for future social improvement. They critiqued the distortions and omissions regarding black women attempting a gynocritical inquiry into the black women's aesthetics as well as the literary conditions. Black feminists held an interest for biographical research, receptionist modes of inquiry, and socio-political analysis. Most were committed to cultural criticism. The black feminist cultural poetics saw literature as a rhythmical (language) expression of the feelings of the author, in keeping with her experience as an endeavour to provide the reader with a peek. Black feminists did not evaluate a work from the conventional Western aesthetics' standards since the Afro-American literature did not follow them strictly. Significantly the black feminists held great sympathy and empathy for the black lesbian literature. Interestingly the black feminists who lead the movement identified themselves with the Third World women, often aligning with the "women of colour." These women of colour represented a broad panethnic group that includes women who are African American, Asian American, Latino American, and

Native American women as well as indigenous peoples of underdeveloped countries around the globe. The 1980s achievements for the black women writers and critics brought them the attention of the leading black male intellectuals, especially Amiri Baraka, and Mari Evans, fostering rapprochement. McDowell and Stephen Henderson worried about the lack of interest for the theoretical developments such as structuralism and poststructuralism, among black feminist critics. Even though Henderson complained against the lack of contributions from Houston Baker, Henry Louis Gates, and others interested in vanguard critical theory he was cognizant of the fact that certain sociological matters might be more pressingly urgent for the black feminists. The next new frontier for the academic black feminists during 1980s seemed destined to be critical theory however critics such as Barbara Christian expressed their skeptic anxiousness over such growth of the critical theory, this anti-theory argument however crystallized in Christian's 1987 essay, "The Race for Theory" which was a scathing attack on the theoretical development of poststructuralism.

There exist several cross connections between womanists and the ecofeminists. Both recognize the systems of oppression as interconnected. Black feminist Patricia Hill Collins enlists two works, namely, Angela Davis' *Women, Race, and Class* (1981) and Audre Lorde's (1984) classic volume *Sister Outsider* which consent with the view. In an essay entitled "Toward a Politics of Empowerment" included in her *Black Feminist Thought: Knowledge, Consciousness, and the Politics of Empowerment* (2009) Collins asserts that domination encapsulates within the tools of structural, disciplinary, hegemonic, and interpersonal domains of power. These remind of Warren's detailed exploration of the dynamics of unjust domination and oppressions in the *Ecofeminist Philosophy* (2000). To briefly explain, the structural domain of power

encompasses how social institutions are organized to reproduce black women's subordination and the subordination of the multiple "Others." The disciplinary domain of power (reminds of Foucault) operates not through explicit racist or sexist social policies but through "bureaucratic hierarchies and techniques of surveillance" (Collins: 299). The hegemonic variant writes Collins operates through school curricula, religious teachings, community cultures, family histories and the mass media in validating unjust oppressions of non-dominant groups. Lastly, the interpersonal domain of power operates in bringing domination by replacing: "...cultural ways of knowing with...hegemonic ideologies that...justify practices of other domains of power" (Collins: 306). She writes:

...the matrix of domination is structured along certain axes race, gender, class, sexuality, and nation as well as how it operates through interconnected domains of power structural, interpersonal, disciplinary, and hegemonic reveals that the dialectical relationship linking oppression and activism would suggest. This inclusive perspective enables African-American women to avoid labelling one form of oppression as more important than others...(Collins:308).

Françoise d'Eaubonne talks of sexual control (cause of overpopulation) and the control on production (cause of surplus production) by man these issues are echoed even in the U. S. Black feminist thought. A Black feminist chronicles, while White women were:

...assigned the duty of reproducing the national group's population...U.S. population policies broadly defined, aim to discourage black women from having children, claiming that black women make poor mothers and that their children end up receiving handouts from the state...White women are

encouraged to increase their fertility... assisted by...technologies...fertility of undocumented women of color is seen as a threat...especially if such women's children gain citizenship and apply for public services...(Collins :249).

Both ecofeminism and womanism recognize the social constructedness of the negative images of women. Where ecofeminists like Mary Daly talk of "Hags" and "Crones" in her *Gyn/Ecology*, Patricia Collins talks of the "matriarchs" and "welfare mothers" (Collins 92). Also, both ecofeminists (even though some amongst them try to distance themselves from it all ecofeminist positions lapse into it eventually) and Black feminists are charged of being essentialists, focusing on women's physiological and social experiences. Both qualify under the category of "essentialism per se" if one was to judge according to Kathy Ferguson's categorization of essentialisms in her *The Man Question: Visions of Subjectivity in Feminist Theory* (1993). Womanists as well as the ecofeminists, hold a holistic view of nature and are sensitive to environmental ethics third theory, that is, an ecocentric view of nature that the environment has an intrinsic value and has its rights as much as any other part of the creation. The first two theories hold an anthropocentric view that man has the moral responsibility towards environment and animal life because of his sense of reason. Even though both ecofeminists and the women of color celebrate the affinity of women with nature both are aware of the social constructivist aspect of it as well. Also, both cultural ecofeminists (like Mary Daly) and certain womanists (like Alice Walker herself) seek answers in spiritual alternatives.

In the essay "Grass-Roots Ecofeminism: Activating Utopia" in the Greta Gaard and Patrick D. Murphy edited work *Ecofeminist Literary Criticism: Theory, Interpretation, Pedagogy*, Cathleen McGuire and Colleen McGuire in the description of the analysis of Marge Piercy's work

Woman on the Edge of Time by the ecofeminist study group, give the verbatim reproduction of the discussion by the group as also memorialized in the September 7, 1992, issue of The EVE Newsletter. According to this discussion, several women commented on Piercy's positive depiction of death as a natural passage in the cycle of life. Ecofeminists (as well as prepatriarchal peoples and most current indigenous cultures) regard death with respect, and not a force to be feared or controlled as it is under patriarchy. This statement also holds true for the gospel tradition which saw death as the passage to the better afterlife. Though the spirituals also fall in the same category to an extent their concern with this-worldly affairs place them somewhat closer to the radical feminist agenda, that was a great source for the development of the ecofeminist thought. Emerging during the second wave of ecofeminism, radical feminism had a distinct character from all other feminisms. The 1970s saw two of its tendencies surface, namely, radical cultural feminism and radical rationalist feminism. While radical cultural feminism exalted and celebrated femininity especially in an identification with nature, radical rationalist feminism viewed the woman-nature connection, and in turn female biology, as the ground-zero of women's historical oppression. Cultural feminists celebrated the affinity with Mother Earth which they saw as the embodiment of the spiritual, as opposed to science and technology. It is the core from which emerged the ecofeminism's understanding that the domination of nature and the domination of women are fundamentally connected. However there tendency of this thought to jeopardize ecofeminism's commitment to thwart dualism, and an almost obviating tendency to universalize all women's experience is apparent. Rationalistic feminism on the other hand bequeathed ecofeminism a mature critique of the politics of oppression and the hierarchies. The seventies radical feminism gave ecofeminism:

the analysis of nature, the hierarchies, politics of oppression, and a holistic spiritual understanding leaving out all that was undesirable within cultural feminism, namely, separatism, and universalizing of women's experience. The nineties radical feminism is not a straight follow up of the seventies radical feminism, for it is a classification for all feminists who do not fit into the liberal mainstream, and foster agendas that are different from the set jurisdiction of the term. This link of the nineties radical feminism reflects the attitude of the blues to a certain degree.

In the essay "Toward an Ecofeminist Standpoint Theory: Bodies as Grounds" authored by Deborah Slicer as included in the work *Ecofeminist Literary Criticism: Theory, Interpretation, Pedagogy*, edited by Greta Gaard and Patrick D. Murphy, Slicer states that environmentally concerned women attend to their bodies as materialized starting points for theorising similarly materialized nature. She makes this suggestion keeping a sympathetic approach to the standpoint theory, especially its potential for ecofeminism, concentrating on the political definitions of matter, of how bodies are seen as matter and how women are seen as bodies. She makes plain that such definitions are qualified by species membership (based on class and race) by whether one is cognizant or not. The standpoint theories of human consciousness as developed by Hegel and Marx, and defended by renowned names such as and Harding, bell hooks, Uma Narayan, Donna Haraway, and Patricia Collins were not a feminist invention. According to Uma Narayan 'epistemic Privilege' claims that individuals within an oppressed group have a more immediate-intricate knowledge about the nature of the oppressions than people who are non-members of the oppressed group.

Some ecofeminists have made claims relevant to the standpoint theory. One among them is Ariel Salleh who claimed that the work one does and one's orientation to the world and to self... moulds one's thinking

which may be more or less materially aware, dualistic, or use-oriented. For Salleh the "feminine" social identity is more eco-friendly than the "masculine" identity, but by this she did not mean to essentialize though her claim may be seen as romantic. Karen J. Warren and Jim Cheney propose that women's voices must be privileged for bringing women's voices to the centre (methodologically and epistemologically) that will help an overall critique and revisioning of the concept of nature and the moral dimensions of human-nature relationship. Cheney believed all the marginalized groups mediate dualisms and are 'care' oriented while Warren wanted these marginalized voices to be heard. Plumwood gave a call for a scenario where men and women are both seen as "continuous" with nature and not alien from it. Plumwood suggests that the masculine self employs reason. She explains that the untangling this construction does, does not entail a denial of women's continuity with nature or an uncritical embracing of it but to make these categories more permeable women create culture, too, and to think over carefully the normative standards that these radically different socially constructed ontologies encompass. Plumwood's ideas of men and women both being continuous to nature may be agreeable but to some they are rather underdeveloped for she does not clearly provide answers to questions such as: how have women been excluded from oppositional culture? What compels a discomfort with dualism and a deeper questioning? How are women's lives comparatively less directly oppositional to nature? What qualities privilege women's experiences? And what sort of women is Plumwood talking about? Vandana Shiva too makes her ecofeminist standpoint, and comparatively specific one. As critics and outsiders rural women are involved in a struggle against institutions that threaten their traditional social and economic status through imperialization and cultural colonization. In their day to day lives they work in sync with the land to provide physical sustenance for their families mediating traditional

Western dualisms. Shiva's *Staying Alive* offers a local, detailed, and concrete account of violence against women and nature starting with a group of marginalised voices in theorizing a stand point ecofeminist. Shiva, like Patricia Hill Collins, defends standpoint theory, which is ontologically at both the Western and the Indian associations of women and nature, and it theorizes an alternative that collapses many Western dualisms. It rejects Western ontological conceptions of nature, women, non-European races, the poor (as all "nature"), animals, and the land, proposing a different normative attitude. But even Shiva's view is devoid of problems for gender is not deconstructed or contextualised within Indian culture. The lives of the rural women are often romanticized and women are seen as members of a non-western culture with its own non dualised ontological value framework that a vast majority of women, living in industrialised societies, do not have. Western women do not share a non dualised ontological and value framework of their own or share an intimate knowledge of the land, so can the assumption that they could achieve a standpoint in relation to nature be made?

For many feminists an association with nature was a culturally created essentialist idea which saw women as "other," as an outsider, and, more specifically, as body, as passive matter, and keepers of bodies, yet others situate women within essentialist sounding space when they claim that women are ontologically situated in culture and therefore is "human" enough to be endowed with the full continuum of anthropocentric human privileges. Debates to situate women within the "nature" and "culture" spectrum by the ecofeminists have been in vain. Deborah avers that what we have what we have is a critique of the politics of gender but not a thorough critique of our dualised conception of human identity or an attempt to develop an alternative culture which would recognise human identity as continuous with and not alien continuous with and not alien

from, nature as Plumwood also avers. Slicer suggests that while fruitful to look at women's perspectives as material caregivers and as our identities as materialised / naturalised "others" to initiate standpoint theorizing what is required is a third starting place, our bodies. Bodies that also become a point of focus for the women in blues. Slicer's claims seem rather apt in bridging the gap between the politics of the female "bodies" for women of color and the ecofeminists.

The gospel scene took hold in 1890s undergoing a transition till the 1920s. In between this period emerged what is known as the solo gospel marking the dawn of the female voice. The 1910s and the 1920s was the period that saw the sanctified movement while the 1930s were the years that saw stalwarts like Thomas Andrew, Dorsey, and Sallie Martin. The 1940s that followed saw gospel gain new acclaim, a period that gave African American music scene people like Sister Rosetta Tharpe, ushering in an era when gospel entered nightclubs and theatres. However the years that followed the years of the World War II marked the golden era of gospel when it became a national commercial phenomenon. Gospel music is reflective of a sense of the historical past of Black Americans transmitting the agency with which Black Americans concocted for themselves an agent for spiritual sustenance while simultaneously managing to reinforce their cultural identity. Enumerating certain "functional dimensions" of Black music, Deborah Smith Pollard, in the essay "That Text, That Timber; Introducing Gospel Announcer Edna Tatum" enlists sound, solicitational frames (call-and-response), meta communication, metaphorical language, and the use of rhetorical devices as the key dimensions of black music. Let us recall these assumptions from an ecofeminist perspective. The employment of different nuances or a range of sounds and timbers by the members of the choir to communicate the desired message and effect within gospel music

facilitated a direct connection of the performers with the "timbers" and the human voices that helped in healing as well as a celebration of the culture. This phenomenon establishes the overlapping nature/culture connection often debated within the realm of ecofeminism. Call and response as a technique instils a certain naturalness to gospel music while simultaneously also qualifying it to the ontological side of culture within the "nature" and "culture" cartesian dualism. The interactive character of gospel performances were in the domain of what in the language of ecofeminism would be referred to as the domain of "care."

The gospel scene before the 1890s remained mainly dominated by the male-(voice)-centric structure, followed by the transition period of 1890s till the 1920s. However, significant shift in this structural set up of the churches occurred during this period. The 1910s and 1920s saw the flourishing of the sanctified movement across the country as African Americans migrated to urban centres. Women constituted the bulk of church members, assuming prominent roles in the building of churches and spreading of the faith further shaping their distinctive musical style. These female missionaries took to the streets aiming to reach out to the unregenerate. Their music that was an evolved version of the mode of worship, an evangelical tool that helped catch the attention of the passers bys. With the advent of mass communication technology this became available in the form of sound recordings. Some of these entered the recording studio, seeking to turn the new thus moving beyond the realm of the church into the commercial arena. Some churches began as a protest countering the high-brow Negro Protestant congregations which came about as a consequence of a rise in education and wealth. The elements and style of worship in these churches is more African than Christian. In the first half of the twentieth century while the gospel quartet tradition was dominated by men, women emerged as great

innovators in the solo gospel springing from a few small churches that represented the margins of the black religious life. Solo gospel is a style of sacred singing marked by an upbeat tempo and intense rhythms generated through percussive instrumental accompaniment. The humble beginnings of gospel evolved to become the most commercial form in sacred music in the U.S., engendering an atmosphere congenial for the amalgamation of the sacred with the secular and the coming together of the local black communities and the White mainstream popular culture. Gospel helped African Americans delve in profound thinking over subjects concerning the nature of faith and in understanding the anatomy of racial identity. Solo gospel helped create a congenial space for women at a time when they were barred from preaching. This middle class push towards evangelism branched out into secular sounds like that of the blues and the jazz traditions amidst the African American community, offering liberatory experiences especially for the women swarming in to join these music genres. The term "gospel" itself came to be applied to a body of sacred music after 1920s, but the impetus for solo gospel tradition emerged in the 1890s with the emergence of a small religious movement that would eventually coalesce into a set of independent black congregations and denominations known as the sanctified church. On the contrary end of the solo gospel existed the tradition symbolised by the Fisk Jubilee Singers who expertise in performing classically arranged slave spirituals.

Emerging from the margins, the solo gospel tradition blossomed in the music of singers like Bessie Johnson who took to the task of informing the audience of the holistic divine ways to enhance their lives. She achieved this end through the volume of her song, increasing it and edging towards a rough gravel, quickened tempo, uneven singing, and occasional shout sounds to make her point. Though initially she began at a considerably slow tempo, slowly acquiring momentum as her singing group joined in for the performance this fervent display was a direct

indicator of her emotions. Her solo singing was rooted in the vernacular sounds of slavery and is characteristically seated in the traditional singing of the sanctified churches that incorporated strong guttural sounds and riffs. Her song delivery is characteristically textured and in full-throated local style. She spearheaded the group called The Memphis Sanctified Singers. Let us make an ecofeminist evaluation of some of Bessie's songs. "He's Got Better Things For You," a simple three verse and chorus (repeated after every verse stanza), is a gospel song offering hope for those suffering, with the promise of salvation and reward in heaven, contrary to the traditional concept of holy retribution, escape from punishment in hell, through the completion of "better things" that God seems to have planned for the individuals. It is interesting to note the lines "He got better things for you, / No one on earth can do." From a womanist-ecofeminist perspective these lines take on a certain dualistic character where God becomes superior to "earth" itself, contrary to the holistic view of the earth in the wake of a pantheist womanist-ecofeminist approach to the universe. Within the lyrics are references to the story of Cornelius, a centurion (Roman) who on being instructed by an angel sent for Peter as instructed baptized himself in the name of Jesus Christ, became the first gentile to join the ranks of the earliest Christians, and a reference to the story of virgin Mary, the earthly mother of Christ himself, she was sent to Jerusalem to be made "new." The idea of the white male Christian God though comparatively soft in approach in terms of the contempt of retribution (of reward and punishment) the following lyrics to Johnson's song "He's Got the Whole World, in His Hands" add emphasis where God has everything in His hands, then be it, "the whole wide world," "the wind," "the rain," "the little biddy baby," or "you," and "me."

It is important to understand that African Americans constantly turned to religion in order to make sense of the world around and therefore their worship practices constantly kept shifting and modified. The

record
the co
migrat
world
mecha
home
gender
where
women
and sol
minister
were no
malprac
persistin
these w
relations
female a
taboo. T
values th
capture
makeup
religious
W
making
access t
reformers
institution
maintain
like the bl
(first at loc

recordings made by Johnson and by the Fisk Jubilee Singers embodied the competing meanings that African Americans gave to religion. With the migration of the 1920s African Americans entered the urban-industrial world carrying with them their rural sensibilities that served as the defence mechanism. A consequence of this was the turning of the churches into a home ground for women, which in turn marked a change in the existent gender relations much beyond the explicit circumstance of the churches where men were the authority though majority membership was that of women. They were many in number and as members cooked the meals and sold them and raised the money. By the 1920s and 1930s women ministers of independent congregations began to emerge. These women were no less than social scientists who were deeply troubled with the malpractices. While such efforts were successful to a certain degree the persisting strength of gender proscriptions is evident from the trials of these women. Owing to these differences, there existed a strained relationship between Pentecostalism and the mainline religions. Since female authority attracted derision female preaching was considered a taboo. The 1920s and the 1930s marked a cultural thrust to find secular values that were an amalgam of spiritual as well as the values that could capture the meaning and essence of the society. Such a structural makeup of the society built in the process brought about tremendous religious plurality.

Women used this opportunity in ushering in a significant change, making use of the material and the spiritual resources that they had access to in order to carve out a space for themselves performing as reformers and missionaries. While the main concern of the middle-class institutions was social reform, women in Church of God in Christ maintained a deep interest in missionary work. Middle-class institutions like the black Baptist Women that established separate women's societies (first at local and state levels and eventually to the national level) and was

the autonomous wing of the National Baptist Convention, and the National Training Institute for Women (that black Baptist Women set out to professionalise the domestic work) that created formal training programs for the African American women to evade the monotonous drudgery of the domestic work and to help uplift it to the status of respectability. Categorising political activism as a shortcoming for religion because it focuses entirely on social issues focusing mainly on the issue of salvation, The Women's Department under the Church of God in Christ encouraged women to reach out to the public. It attached great value to the histories of the women who had contributed to the spiritual missionary work. Women missionaries like Lizzie Roberson pursued the task of evangelizing in the Church of God in Christ. Music played a significant role in the work of these women missionaries. Women like Sister Rosetta Tharpe built on the foundation that sanctified women made viable. While the 1910s and 1920s saw the sanctified movement flourish placing women in prominent roles of missionaries the 1930s saw this religious movement extend from the margins to the centre of black religious life. The main agents responsible for this shift were Thomas Andrew Dorsey and his associates notable amongst whom was the former sanctified singer Sallie Martin. Sanctified women were responsible for the vast spread of the gospel music during the 1920s and 1930s. Let us turn to these women to fathom the role they had to play in the development of gospel music.

Sister Rosetta Tharpe's journey from an itinerant missionary singing in churches and city streets after being raised in the Church of God in Christ, to the zenith of stardom as one of gospel music's pioneers has been markedly interesting. The cultural shock she felt on being exposed to the world of moving images on the big screen made her to literally run out of the theatre. In 1930s when Sister Rosetta Tharpe became the name synonymous with the identity of the person responsible for pushing the horizon of sacred music way beyond the realm of the churches into that

the commercial. Daughter of a zealous missionary Katie Bell Nubin, Tharpe was raised in a sheltered home environment away from the commercial amusements. Having nestled in religious circles that were mainly dominated by women as a child Tharpe's understanding of women bonding is reflected in her 1956 comment:

I remember we used to live in the country, and the womens you know, they wouldn't think about anything. They would go to one another's house and they would hate to leave one another. That's when the sweetness was in the land then....We used to stay at one another's house and when our friend get ready to leave, we wouldn't want to go. (Tharpe, Sister Rosetta. *The Gospel Truth*. Live Recording. Mercury MG 20412, 1956.)

It is claimed that Rosetta Tharpe could make a guitar "talk." Jerma A. Jackson's comment sheds light in this claim:

...she adopts a technique used by blues musicians, who piled their craft on the same streets where she evangelised. Making a guitar "talk" involved playing single notes rather than chords, turning the instrument into an extension of the vocal line and creating a second voice that made for a more dynamic performance. In addition to playing single notes, blues musicians slid devices such as pocket knives and bottle-necks along the guitar strings to reproduce shadings of the human voice. (40)

First crossover artist in gospel music and the first recording star she was given the epithets of the "original soul sister," and the "grandmother of rock and roll." In the song "Strange Things Happening Every Day" Tharpe makes reference to the miraculous things that take shape in everyday life because of the grace of God. She is affirming faith in the divine. But for such miracles to happen one must turn righteously on his path. Her voice

and the belief in all sorts of miracles possible on earth unexplainable from the standards of science, representative of the patriarchal oppressive system of domination locates her within the "nature" spectrum of the ontological dualism. The lyrics to "The Train" express a similar sentiment, while her "Ain't No Grave Hold My Body Down" celebrates the unrelenting nature of the soul. Tharpe affirms her ecofeminist sensibility in these lyrics. She thwarts the oppressive patriarchal system that stresses on the idea of death as something to be feared. She readily accepts it and waits for it being cognizant of its transitory nature she knows that her spirit shall endure after, an idea that womanists affirm in their pantheist understanding of the divine.

Sallie Martin was deeply influenced by the sanctified church as a teenager in Georgia. Sanctified women made on road spiritual mission trips from Chicago to Cincinnati with an objective of building churches and helping souls in salvation. Sallie Martin took a similar trip in the mid-1930s. Migrating to Chicago, associating herself with a small congregation on the city's South side, later she formed a gospel choir in Cincinnati, however in 1932 the music scene began to undergo a metamorphosis as Thomas Dorsey emerged on the scene forming a gospel chorus at Pilgrim Baptist Church, Chicago. Dorsey introduced upbeat rhythms that matched the exuberance of the sanctified worship. Together Dorsey and Martin were responsible for raising gospel to the stature of institutional legitimacy by bringing it somewhat closer to the centre occupied by the much cherished arranged spirituals, from the margins. This collaboration through music took a step towards entrepreneurial black capitalism which facilitated advantages of modest profits and commercial distribution while remaining tied to the values and goals of the communities. Martin rescued Dorsey's sheet music dreams taking over the task of travelling and singing followed by selling, in the run establishing a sound self-sustained enterprise. Martin's experiences at Cincinnati sheds lights on the sense of equality

with which God for her saw man/woman. She explained at the National Convention of Gospel Choirs and Choruses (Welcome to NCGCC, 9, Grant collection): I could not interest the pastor/I organized what we call a/community gospel chorus. She further explains how if confronted by an angry pastor and called upon in a conference "the Lord guided my tongue." She formed the Sallie Martin Singers in which Cora Martin, her daughter, Dinah Washington (then known as Ruth Jones), and Sallie's brother Joe May featured. She started her own publishing house, after a dispute with Dorsey in 1940 called the Martin and Morris Music, Inc., in partnership with Kenneth Morris. The promise of the land of liberation, from all earthly man-made suffering is expressed in the lyrics to "On Jordan's Stormy Banks." Just as the ecofeminists understand death as a natural passage in the cycle of life, much like certain indigenous cultures like India (where the belief of multiple rebirths of the soul exists there exists spiritual logic to death which therefore also affirms life in the form of incarnation), death as a force that is respected offering an escape from the sufferings, is contrary to the fear instilling patriarchal controlling system. She praises God's grace in the hope instilled song "God Put a Rainbow in the Cloud" as if the rainbow was a silver lining on a day devoid of the sun. The association of one's feelings with the surrounding nature is a key aspect of ecofeminism. Here the comfort and the reliability Sallie Martin finds in surrounding nature imagery beautifully illustrates this.

Another star embellished name within the field of gospel music is that of Mahalia Jackson. Mahalia Jackson's deep affinity with the earth and deep belongingness and feeling of home in the lap of nature is made apparent through her deep vocals for her rendition of the song "The Green Leaves of Summer." The anti-war streak that exists within ecofeminists (who also made demonstrations against nuclear plants) is reflected in the lyrics to "Down By The Riverside." Her "Elijah Rock" is yet another example of Mahalia's womanist-ecofeminist sensibility that embraces a pantheist

view of God. Another significant song sung by Mahalia Jackson is "Go Tell It on the Mountain." The reference to Jesus Christ as the "Savior" is of great importance. African American women along with their entire community irrespective of gender were awaiting their freedom and examples like those of Christ and Moses offered them the needed hope. The incorporation of the nature imagery in the lyrics to depict a feeling of exuberance and happiness is significant.

Dinah Washington has been referred to as the "queen of the blues," a gospel singer, a jazz artist, and as somebody soulful even before soul music made appearance. She started as a gospel singer and later turned to jazz. She was greatly inspired by the singers Bessie Smith and Billie Holiday. Starting at an early age of eighteen, Dinah Washington made her way through a blatant race market. She had a strong voice that could cut through and make a lasting impression. The audience connected well with her style of singing to the accompaniment of the lush sounds of woodwinds and strings. She migrated from the South to the mainstream music industry in the North but brought with her the flavour of the high end south. She could relate with the low life of Harlem as well as her elite audiences. Her "Evil Gal Blues" (1944) are the essence of who she really was, that is, the elite Southerner making her way through the heart of all kinds of audiences. Dinah Washington was known for her temper but even though off stage she had a very strong personality and could be rude under strict scrutiny of piano players and her willingness to only associate with artists who knew what they were doing was because of her perfectionism. Her music was flawless and her womanist-ecofeminist sensibility is visible in her songs. For instance in "A Stranger on Earth" (1964). The song beautifully depicts the image of alienation in the wake of racism. While the speaker realizes her worth, "fools" that "belong" seem to be oblivious of it. Truly this sense of worth that she understands is because of the understanding of the value of all things, in other words the principle of

oneness that ecofeminists and womanists believe is the spiritual pantheist truth. The false sense of worth that she has to "prove" is only because of the shallow sense of value attached to "culture" within the ontological boundaries. Another significant song by Dinah Washington is "This Bitter Earth" (1960) where the feeling of dejection in love, general as well as amorous, are projected onto nature, "earth." Earth without "fruit," and a life "like the dust/That hides the glow of a rose" conjure the atmosphere of bareness and desolation that makes the earth "bitter," and cold, where young age early. The singer may be singing but the inner voice is crying. Dinah seems to be looking for an answer to her "call" of love, then perhaps the "bitter earth/ May not be so bitter after all," for the singer doubts herself saying "What good am I?/Heaven only knows" as to what her worth without sharing love would be. The womanist ecofeminist idea of love that is all inclusive in its rich continuum can be applied to these words.

Most of the gospel music publishing studios that took shape in the 1940s were either led by or partnered by women such as Roberta Martin, Sallie Martin, and Lillian Bowles. The essence of the gospel music for women remained the idea of music as an act of communion with God rather than individual volition. This concept provided women with the leverage to nurture and celebrate their musical talent even though the pulpit was dominated by men. Women missionaries could freely indulge in their own singular styles of missionary work, combining music and teaching; or simply using their musical abilities to put across the spiritual message.

Work cited

Collins, Patricia Hill. *Black Feminist Thought: Knowledge, Consciousness, and the Politics of Empowerment*. NY: Routledge, 2009. Print.

McGuire, Cathleen and Colleen McGuire. "Grass-Roots Ecofeminism: Activating Utopia." *Ecofeminist Literary Criticism: Theory,*

Interpretation, Pedagogy. Eds. Greta Gaard and Patrick D. Murphy. Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 1998. 186-203. Print.

Slicer, Deborah. "Toward an Ecofeminist Standpoint Theory: Bodies as Grounds." *Ecofeminist Literary Criticism: Theory, Interpretation, Pedagogy*. Eds. Greta Gaard and Patrick D. Murphy. Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 1998. Print.

Pollard, Deborah Smith. "That Text, That Timbre: Introducing Gospel Announcer Edna Tatum." *Black Women and Music: More than the Blues*. Eds. Eileen M. Hayes and Linda F. Williams. Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 2007. Print.

Bo
(J&
stat
hos
qua
cou
side
bee
targ
rece
terr
mak
surv

Keyw

Introc

they a
studyi
to nev
reveal

*Assista